

MARKETING OF SORGHUM IN AKOLA DISTRICT OF MAHARASHTRA

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Abstract

This study revealed that the marketing channels for Jowar (Sorghum) in Akola District, Maharashtra, focusing on the cost, margin, efficiency, and price spread associated with each channel. The study identifies three primary marketing pathways: direct producer-to-consumer sales (Channel I), sales through wholesalers and retailers (Channel II), and sales involving retailers (Channel III). The research utilizes a systematic multi-stage stratified random sampling technique, collecting primary data through personal interviews. The results reveal that Channel I, the direct marketing route, is the most efficient with the lowest marketing costs and a high efficiency of 46.49. Channels II and III, incorporating intermediaries, exhibit significantly lower efficiencies 4.65 and 5.69 respectively) and higher price spreads, indicating greater economic burdens for producers and consumers. These findings highlight the detrimental impact of intermediaries on market dynamics. The study advocates for reducing intermediary involvement to enhance marketing efficiency, improve producer profitability, and ensure fair pricing for consumers. This strategy promises to empower local farmers and promote sustainable agricultural practices.

Keywords— Marketing channels, Jowar (Sorghum), Marketing cost Efficiency, Price spread.

Introduction

The marketing of agricultural products is crucial for the economic empowerment of farmers and the overall development of rural areas. In India, Jowar (Sorghum) is a significant crop, particularly in regions like Maharashtra, where it contributes to both food security and income generation. This research focuses on the marketing channels for Jowar in Akola District.

The study aims to analyse the cost, margin, efficiency, and price spread across different marketing channels, employing a multi-stage stratified random sampling technique to ensure comprehensive data collection. Previous studies have emphasized the importance of efficient marketing systems for improving farmer incomes. In this context, the role of intermediaries in agricultural marketing has been a critical area of investigation, with findings indicating that excessive intermediary involvement often leads to inflated consumer prices and reduced producer profits. The research builds on these insights by providing a detailed examination of the marketing channels in Akola District. By understanding the dynamics and efficiency of each channel, this study aims to identify strategies that can enhance market access, reduce costs, and increase profitability for Jowar producers.

Objective: To study the marketing of sorghum

Methodology

The study was based on primary data for the year 2023-24, collected from the APMC market of Akola district of Maharashtra, the total 120 producers, 10 wholesalers, 10 retailers were selected for the study. Tabulation method is used for analysis of data along with required statistical tools for the interpretation of the results and to investigate the marketing mechanisms of Sorghum in Akola District of Maharashtra.

Marketing channel

In case of sorghum following marketing, channels were observed in the study area.

Channel-I → Producer → Consumer

Channel-II → Producer → Wholesaler → Retailer → Consumer

Channel-III → Producer → Retailer → Consumer

Marketing cost

The total cost incurred on marketing by various intermediaries involved in the sale and purchase of the commodity till it reaches the ultimate consumer was computed as follow:

$$C = C_f + C_{m1} + C_{m2} + C_{m3} + \dots + C_{mn}$$

Where,

C = Total cost of marketing

C_f = Cost borne by the producer farmer from the produce leaves the farm till the sale of the produce, and

C_{mn} = Cost incurred by the ith middlemen in the process of buying and selling.

Marketing margin

This referred to the net share to the different marketing intermediaries for particular quantity of produce after deducting marketing costs from gross marketing margins at each stage of handling the commodity.

$$MT = \sum (S_i - P_i) / Q_i$$

Where,

MT = Total marketing margin.

S_i = Sell value of a product paid by ith firm.

P_i = Purchase value of a product paid by ith firm.

Q_i = Quantity of product handled by ith firm.

Price spread

It was calculated by taking difference between the price paid by the consumer and the price received by the consumer and the price received by the producer.

Price spread: Consumer's price - Price received by the farmer

$$P_s = C_p - P_f$$

Where,

C_p = Consumer's price

P_f = Price received by the farmer.

Producer's share in consumer's rupee (P_s)

It is the ratio of net price received by producer to the price paid by consumer and can be calculated as follows

$$P_s = \frac{P_f}{P_c} \times 100$$

Where,

P_f = Net price received by the producer

P_c = Price paid by the consumer

2.6 Marketing efficiency (ME)

The marketing efficiency was calculated by using the modified method suggested by Acharya and Agarwal (2001).

$$MME = RP / (MC + MM)$$

Where,

MME = Modified measure of marketing efficiency,

RP = Price paid by consumer or retailers sell price,

MC = Total marketing cost and

MM = Net marketing margin.

Results And Discussion

Marketing Cost of Sorghum Incurred by Producer

The per quintal marketing cost of sorghum incurred by producer in different channels was calculated and is presented in Table 1. The cost incurred by the producer was the highest with Rs. 134.89 per quintal in channel-II followed by Rs.104.32 in channel-III and Rs.56.25 per quintal in channel-I. It was observed that the proportionate expenditure in the total cost was the highest on gunny bag Rs.51.25 (91.11%) in channel-I followed by miscellaneous charges Rs. 5(8.89 %). In channel-II share was highest on gunny bag Rs.50.32 (37.30%),

followed by commission charges Rs.30.13(22.34%), transportation charges Rs. 26.18 (19.40%), Hamali charges Rs.21.26(15.77 %), miscellaneous charges Rs.5(3.71%) and weighing Rs. 2 (1.48%). In channel-III share was highest on gunny bag charges Rs. 51.6 (49.47%), followed by transportation charges Rs. 25.49 (24.44%), Hamali charges Rs. 20.23(19.39%), miscellaneous charges Rs. 5(4.79%) and weighing charges Rs.2 (1.91%) respectively.

Marketing Cost of Sorghum Incurred by Wholesaler

Per quintal marketing cost of sorghum incurred by wholesaler in channel-II, was calculated and is presented in Table 1. The results revealed that the total cost was Rs. 92.99 in channel-II. It was observed that the proportionate expenditure in the total cost was the highest on gunny bag Rs.55.32(55.18%) followed by Hamali charges Rs.21.35(22.96%), Cess fund Rs.18.32(19.71%) and weighing charges

Rs.2(2.15%) in channel-II.

Marketing Cost of Sorghum Incurred by Retailer

Per quintal marketing cost of sorghum incurred by Retailer in channel-II, was calculated and is presented in Table 1. The results revealed that the total cost was Rs. 91.22 in channel-II and 79.87 in channel-III. It was observed that the proportionate expenditure in the total cost was the highest on gunny bag Rs.50(54.82%) followed by Hamali charges Rs.20.64(22.63%), transportation charges Rs.14.58(15.98%), miscellaneous charges Rs.4(4.38%) and weighing charges Rs.2(2.19%) in channel-II. In channel-III share was highest on gunny bag charges Rs. 51.24 (64.15%), followed by Hamali charges Rs. 20.63(25.83%), miscellaneous charges Rs. 6(7.51%) and weighing charges Rs.2 (2.51%) respectively.

Table 1. Marketing cost of sorghum incurred by different intermediaries

(Rs. /quintal)				
Sr.No.	Particulars	Channel I	Channel II	Channel III
A	Marketing cost incurred by Producer			
1	Packing charges (Gunny bag)	51.25	50.32	51.60
2	Transport charges	-	26.18	25.49
3	Hamali	-	21.26	20.23
4	weighing	-	2	2
5	Commission charges	-	30.13	-
6	Miscellaneous Charges	5	5	5
	Sub total	56.25	134.89	104.32
B	Marketing cost incurred by Wholesaler			
1	Packing charges (Gunny bag)	-	51.32	-
2	Transport charges	-	0	-
3	Hamali	-	21.35	-
4	Cess fund	-	18.32	-
5	weighing	-	2	-
6	Commission charges	-	0	-
7	Miscellaneous Charges	-	0	-
	Sub total	-	92.99	-
C	Marketing cost incurred by Retailer			
1	Packing charges (Gunny bag)	-	50	51.24
2	Transport charges	-	14.58	-
3	Hamali	-	20.64	20.63
4	weighing	-	2	2
5	Commission charges	-	-	-
6	Miscellaneous Charges	-	4	6
	Sub total	-	91.22	79.87
	Total Marketing cost	56.25	319.1	184.19

Producer's share in consumer's rupee

The producer's share in consumer's rupee was the highest (97.85%) in channel-I followed by channel-III (82.44%) and it was lowest in channel-II (78.52%). The lowest share in channel-II could be because of the reason that the cultivators marketed their produce through commission agents/wholesalers and retailers who took maximum share from the consumer's price (Table 2) The producer's share in consumer's rupee was the highest (97.85%) in channel-I in which cultivators sold their produce directly to Consumers. As the Consumers demanded only selective and quality grains due to elimination of middlemen intervening between the producers and consumers in channel-I, the producer's share was maximum as well as price received

by growers was also more. However, a smaller number of producers sold their produce through channel-I and channel-III.

Price spread

Price spread is the difference between price paid by consumer and price received by producer. This consists of marketing costs and margins of the different intermediaries. The costs and margins of agency in different channels were worked out and details are presented in Table. It is observed from the Table 2 that, the net per quintal cost incurred were Rs.56.25, Rs. 628.09 and Rs.524.23 in Channel I, II, and III, respectively. Per quintal cost was high in Channel II because so many intermediaries included in that channel and produce was marketed to distant markets.

Table 2. Channel wise Marketing Cost, Price Spread in Sorghum Marketing

(Rs. /quintal)				
SN.	Particulars	Channel I	Channel II	Channel III
A)	Gross price received by farmer	2615.23	2430.45	2565.35
1	Marketing cost	56.25	134.89	104.32
2	Net price realized	2558.98	2295.56	2461.03
B	Wholesaler			

1	Price paid (purchase price)	-	2430.45	-
2	Marketing cost	-	92.99	-
3	Marketing margin	-	161.81	-
4	Price received (selling price)	-	2685.25	-
C)	Retailer			
1	Price paid (purchase price)	-	2685.25	2565.35
2	Marketing cost	-	91.22	79.87
3	Marketing margin	-	147.18	340.04
4	Price received (selling price)	-	2923.65	2985.26
D)	Consumer			
1	Price paid	2615.23	2923.65	2985.26
2	Price spread	56.25	628.09	524.23
3	MC+MM	56.25	628.09	524.23
4	Marketing efficiency	46.49	4.65	5.69
5	Producer share in consumers rupees	97.85	78.52	82.44

Table 3. Marketing Efficiency of Sorghum

S.N	Particulars	Channel I	Channel II	Channel III
1	Net price received by the farmer	2558.98	2295.56	2461.03
2	Total marketing cost	56.25	319.10	184.19
3	Marketing margin	-	308.99	340.04
4	MM+MC	56.25	628.09	524.23
5	Price paid by consumer	2615.23	2923.65	2985.26
6	Marketing efficiency ratio	46.49	4.65	5.69

Marketing efficiency

It can be observed from Table 3 that the direct marketing channel (Channel I) is the most efficient, with the lowest costs and highest efficiency, benefiting both producers and consumers. Conversely, the involvement of multiple intermediaries in Channels II and III significantly increases the price spread and reduces marketing efficiency, highlighting the impact of intermediary costs and margins on the overall market dynamics of Jowar.

Conclusion

The research on Jowar marketing channels in Akola district highlights significant disparities in marketing efficiency, cost, and price spread across different channels.

In marketing of Sorghum, channel-I (Producer - Consumer) was profitable because marketing efficiency, producer's share in consumer's rupee and net price received by producer was reported higher and this channel also incurred less marketing cost. Similarly highest marketing cost was reported in channel-II and III; less producer's share in consumer's price was found in Channel-II and also less marketing efficiency was seen in channel-II. It may be concluded from the present study that marketing channel-I was more effective than channels II and III and therefore channel-I is recommended to

follow for marketing of Sorghum in Akola district Maharashtra.

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